

MEDICAL SCIENCES

VITAMIN D SUPPLEMENTATION AND SLEEP: REVIEW

Shkiryak A.

CEO and chief medical officer “Shkiryak Clinic”

Ukraine

Neurosurgeon

MD, MsSc

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2282-8285>

Khanenko S.

“Shkiryak Clinic”

Ukraine

Family doctor

MD, MBA

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-4237-1158>

Abstract

Background: Vitamin D deficiency is associated with sleep disorders and poor sleep quality. Whether vitamin D supplementation (VDS) helps resolve these problems remains unclear. **Objective:** To systematically review the effect of VDS on sleep quantity, quality, and disorders, and perform a meta-analysis of available data. **Methods:** The reporting of this review followed the PRISMA statement. VDS human interventions studies that reported on sleep quality, quantity, or disorders were included. Medline, CINAHL, EMBASE, PsycInfo, the Cochrane Library, Clinicaltrials.gov, and the ICTRP were searched, in addition to the references of the included articles and previous relevant reviews, without language or time restrictions. Included studies were critically appraised, findings were narratively synthesized, and a meta-analysis was conducted. Furthermore, the overall certainty of the evidence was assessed. **Results:** A total of 19 studies were included (13 randomized controlled trials (RCTs), 1 opportunistic addition to an RCT, 4 pre–post studies, and 1 pre–post study analyzed as a case series); 3 RCTs were meta-analyses. The risk of bias was generally low. Pre–post studies showed a significant improvement in sleep quality with VDS. Similarly, the results of the meta-analysis revealed a statistically significant decrease in the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index with VDS compared with placebo (mean difference, -2.33 (95% CI, $-3.09, -1.57$); $p < 0.001$; $I^2 = 0\%$), with a moderate certainty of evidence. The results regarding the effect of VDS on sleep-related impairment, difficulty, and disorders, as well as sleepiness and restless legs syndrome, were not unanimous. **Conclusions:** VDS is promising in improving sleep quality; however, its effect on sleep quantity and disorders needs to be further investigated.

Keywords: vitamin D, sleep.

INTRODUCTION

Inadequate sleep is a common public health problem of significant personal and societal burden (1). Sleep disorders such as insomnia, obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), excessive daytime sleepiness (EDS) and fatigue, sleep deprivation, and restless legs syndrome (RLS) are increasingly being diagnosed in clinical practice (2). It is estimated that 59% of young adults suffer from a sleep disorder and do not get enough sleep (3) and only 36% of this population reports being free of sleep disturbances (4). Inadequate sleep is an underappreciated determinant of health (5,6) and can lead to short-term and long-term consequences. In the short run, inadequate sleep may result in cognitive and motor performance impairments, which can lead to decreased quality of life and reduced productivity (7,8). In the longer term, cumulative sleep deprivation can serve as a factor in the development and exacerbation of cardiovascular and metabolic diseases, cancer, diabetes mellitus, gastrointestinal disorders, and mental illnesses. Thus, the economic burden of inadequate sleep is substantial, warranting urgent investment in health measures to address this issue (1).

Low vitamin D status is a prevalent condition that has been linked to a wide range of adverse health outcomes (10,11). Growing evidence has demonstrated that vitamin D has a role in sleep regulation (12). Specifically, vitamin D deficiency (VDD) can increase risk of sleep disorders and is associated with sleep difficulties, shorter sleep duration, and nocturnal awakenings in children and adults (13,14,15). The exact mechanisms by which vitamin D regulates sleep are still far from being elucidated. Plausible theories include the presence of vitamin D receptors on areas of the brainstem that are known to be pacemaker cells playing an important role in sleep regulation (16,17), in addition to the potential role of vitamin D in regulating melatonin, the “sleep hormone” (18).

Hence, it is plausible that vitamin D supplementation (VDS) might have a positive effect on sleep disorders, including decreased sleep latency, improved sleep efficiency, and longer sleep duration. Preventing and managing sleep disorders or correcting them by VDS is of public health relevance, given the low cost of this intervention and its effectiveness in other therapeutic areas. Given the lack of conclusive evidence in this regard, we aim to systematically review the available literature on the effect of VDS on sleep quantity, quality,

and sleep disorders, and perform a meta-analysis of the available data.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Criteria for Study Inclusion

Interventional studies, whether controlled or not, conducted on individuals not having diseases or receiving medication known to influence vitamin D metabolism, such as chronic kidney disease or liver disease, with or without sleep disturbances, including vitamin D supplementation in any form, dose, or frequency as intervention, and reporting on the prevalence or severity of sleep disorders (19), such as insomnia disorders, sleep-related breathing disorders, central disorders of hypersomnolence, circadian rhythm sleep–wake disorders, parasomnias, and sleep-related movement disorders, or sleep quantity or quality, were included.

All studies extending supplementation for a minimum of 4 weeks were included in this review to ensure adequate time for the intervention to produce an effect. In addition, controlled studies involving a placebo, or a lower dose, or different form of vitamin D were included. Finally, controlled studies including a co-intervention were included if both arms of the study received the same co-intervention.

Eligible studies were those written in any language, irrespective of publication date (i.e., no language or time limit).

Exclusion criteria included non-original studies (e.g., case reports, case series, editorials, and reviews) and studies conducted on participants with conditions (e.g., chronic kidney disease) or on medications that might have an effect on vitamin D metabolism (e.g., phenytoin, phenobarbital, carbamazepine, and rifampin). Finally, studies evaluating the association between vitamin D status (hypo or hypervitaminosis D) and sleep were not included.

Search Strategy

The author searched Medline via Ovid, the Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL) via EBSCO, EMBASE via Ovid, APA PsycInfo via Ovid, the Cochrane Library, Clinicaltrials.gov, and the International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP). Vitamin D supplementation and sleep were the key concepts followed in the search strategy: for each concept, Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) and keywords were recorded, whereby search terms included vitamin D, cholecalciferol, ergocalciferol or calcidol, combined with sleep or insomnia. The author did not apply any language or publication date restrictions to the search. The author also hand searched the reference lists of included articles and previous relevant reviews for eligible studies.

Study Selection

Studies meeting the inclusion criteria previously specified were identified by screening titles and/or abstracts from electronic scientific databases via Endnote, version X6. Full texts of potentially eligible studies were retrieved. Finally, records in the grey literature search zone were further assessed for eligibility of inclusion.

Data Extraction

For all eligible studies, data related to the features of the study, population groups, interventions given (type, form, and the dose of vitamin D in experimental

groups, comparator, and duration), outcomes, and main findings were extracted and recorded in a data extraction form. When reported as nmol/L, the author converted serum 25OHD to ng/mL by dividing by a factor of 2.496. The author contacted the authors of some included studies to obtain additional data, when they were not reported in the published studies.

Quality Assessment

The Cochrane criteria (sequence generation, allocation concealment, blinding of participants and outcome assessors, incomplete outcome data, and selective outcome reporting) were used as the tool to assess the risk of bias of RCTs included in this review (20). Furthermore, a modified version of the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool (21) (eligibility criteria, measurement of exposure and outcome, control confounding, and follow-up) was used to assess the risk of bias of non-randomized studies. Potential sources of bias for both RCTs and non-randomized studies were graded as low, high, or unclear risk.

Data Synthesis

A narrative composite of the study findings was provided when a meta-analysis was not feasible. Furthermore, author-recorded features of the study, population group characteristics, intervention provided, comparator, and the outcome were included in this composite.

A meta-analysis was conducted when participants, treatments, and outcomes shared similar characteristics to allow pooling. Standard meta-analyses comparing VDS with placebo were performed using RevMan version 5.4 (The Cochrane Collaboration, The Nordic Cochrane Centre). A random-effects model was used for the analysis of more than two studies. The results were reported as the mean difference with 95% confidence intervals. The I^2 statistic was used to assess heterogeneity among different studies.

Quality of Reporting

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses literature search extension (PRISMA-S) checklist and the PRISMA statement were followed for the literature search component (22), and the reporting of this systematic review (23).

RESULTS

Search Results

Out of the 19,051 screened records, 19 studies were included in this systematic review. Out of these studies, thirteen were RCTs (24-36), one was an opportunistic addition to an established randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial (37), four were pre–post studies (38-41), and one was a self-controlled before–after trial, analyzed retrospectively as a case series (42).

Three out of thirteen RCTs generated data that could be combined in the meta-analysis.

Characteristics of Included Studies

Six of the studies were conducted in Iran (25, 27,30,31,34,39), five in the USA (28, 29,32,33,42), one in Ireland (26), one in New Zealand (37), one in KSA (35), one in China (36), one in Turkey (40), and one in the Netherlands (24). The number of participants varied from 5 (31) to 18,353 (32). Two studies were conducted in the pediatric population: children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (40) and ADHD (31), one study was con-

ducted on overweight postmenopausal women (28), another in elderly women (39), and one on community-dwelling older people (24). One study was conducted in patients receiving maintenance methadone treatment (25), one in active-duty warfighters (29), one on veterans with multiple areas of chronic pain and low serum 25(OH)D (42), one on adult patients with urticarial (33), one on fibromyalgia syndrome patients (30), one in patients with chronic low back pain (41), and one on patients with depression with tied anxiety symptoms (36). Finally, one study was conducted on adults with OSA (26), one on adults with sleep disorders (27), two in patients with RLS (35,38), and one on adults with vitamin D deficiency, abdominal obesity, and symptoms of insomnia (34).

In the majority of the studies, the intervention consisted of vitamin D3 supplementation (24, 26,27,28,29,32,33,34,35,37,38,42), two used vitamin D2 supplementation (40,42), and the form of vitamin D was unclear in six trials (25,30,31,36,39,41). Only Sharifan et al. (34) assessed VDS in the form of fortified low-fat milk or low-fat yogurt. The duration of supplementation ranged from 8 weeks (27,30,31,39,41) to a median of 5.3 years (32). The average daily dose of VDS ranged from 1000 IU (29,39) to 7142.85 IU (30,35,42). When reported, compliance with VDS was high in all studies. The majority of the studies were placebo controlled (24,25,26,27,28,30,31,32,35,36,37). In two studies, the comparator was no supplementation (29,39); in one study, it was a lower dose of vitamin D (33); in one study, it was either low-fat milk or yogurt (34). The most assessed outcome was sleep quality, mainly using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) (25,27,28,30,39,41,42).

Sleep Quality

The pre–post studies by Huang et al. (42), Eshaghi et al. (39), and Maheshwari et al. [41] investigated the effect of VDS on sleep quality assessed by the PSQI. All three trials showed a significant improvement in overall sleep quality with VDS. However, the three trials were heterogeneous and did not contain ample information allowing pooling; hence, performing a meta-analysis of their results was impossible.

The four RCTs conducted by Ghaderi et al. (25), Majid et al. (27), Mason et al. (28), and Mirzaei et al. (30) explored the effect of VDS on sleep quality assessed by the PSQI. Only three (25,27,30) provided information and had similar characteristics to allow pooling, whereas the study by Mason et al. (28) did not report on numerical outcomes, and therefore was not included in the meta-analysis. This study showed no significant change in overall sleep quality with VDS and a deterioration in total PSQI among women who repleted their vitamin D levels, concluding that VDS of 2000 IU/d may result in overall worse sleep quality for postmenopausal women with low circulating vitamin D undergoing weight loss.

The three studies included patients undergoing maintenance methadone treatment (25), people with a PSQI ≥ 5 (27), and fibromyalgia syndrome patients (30). The duration of VDS was short (8 (27, 30) to 12 weeks (25)), and the dose was either 3571.42 (25, 27) or 7142.85 IU (30). A statistically significant decrease in the PSQI in the group receiving VDS as compared

with placebo was shown by the meta-analysis (mean difference, -2.33 (95% CI, $-3.09, -1.57$); $p < 0.001$).

Other Outcomes

Disturbed sleeping

The only pre–post study (40) investigating sleep habits and disorders in children with ASD showed that VDS may be beneficial in these patients, as well as healthy individuals with sleep disturbances.

As for RCTs, the effects of VDS on sleep-related impairment, sleep difficulty, and sleep disorders were assessed by McCarthy et al. (29), Okereke et al. (32), and Zhu et al. (36), respectively; the results were not unanimous. While McCarthy et al. (29) showed a statistically significant improvement in sleep-related impairment with VDS, Okereke et al. (32) and Zhu et al. (36) did not report on such findings. In both RCTs, there were non-significant differences in likelihood of sleep problems with VDS compared with placebo after controlling for confounding variables).

Sleepiness

Two RCTs assessed the effect of VDS on sleepiness using different tools (26, 34). The study of Kerley et al. (26), which was conducted on patients with OSA, did not report any difference in sleepiness between the group receiving VDS and those receiving placebo. In contrast, the study by Sharifan et al. (34), which was conducted on patients with insomnia, showed a beneficial effect of vitamin D3-fortified low-fat milk on insomnia symptoms compared with unfortified milk. No effect was detected with vitamin D3-fortified low-fat yogurt compared with unfortified one.

RLS

The pre–post study conducted by Arico et al. (38) found that long-term VDS (6 months) decreased RLS severity in a small population (5 patients). In contrast, the RCT by Wali et al. (35) found no effect of VDS on severity of RLS compared with placebo.

Sleep Problems as Adverse Events of VDS

Sleep problems as an adverse event of VDS were assessed in the two RCTs conducted by Mohammadpour et al. (31), and de Koning et al. (24). Both studies showed no significant difference in sleep problems with VDS versus placebo in children with ADHD or community-dwelling people with depressive symptoms, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the evidence presented in this review suggests a beneficial role of VDS in enhancing sleep quality. These results remain to be interpreted with caution given the limited number of included RCTs and their relatively small sample size. Nevertheless, the positive effects of such supplementation could be considered in clinical practice, especially in the context of beneficial skeletal (56) and pleiotropic extraskeletal effects (57, 58) of vitamin D, as well as the relatively limited cost of VDS. As we could not find enough studies assessing the effect of VDS on sleep disorders, OSA, sleepiness, and RLS, this remains to be explored in future adequately powered, high-quality RCTs.

References

1. Hillman D., Mitchell S., Streatfeild J., Burns C., Bruck D., Pezzullo L. The economic cost of inadequate

- sleep. *Sleep*. 2018;41:zsy083. doi: 10.1093/sleep/zsy083.
2. Skaer T.L., Sclar D.A. Economic implications of sleep disorders. *Pharmacoeconomics*. 2010;28:1015–1023. doi: 10.2165/11537390-000000000-00000.
 3. Sateia M.J. International classification of sleep disorders-third edition: Highlights and modifications. *Chest*. 2014;146:1387–1394. doi: 10.1378/chest.14-0970.
 4. Coren S. The prevalence of self-reported sleep disturbances in young adults. *Int. J. Neurosci*. 1994;79:67–73. doi: 10.3109/00207459408986068.
 5. Luyster F.S., Strollo P.J., Jr., Zee P.C., Walsh J.K. Sleep: A health imperative. *Sleep*. 2012;35:727–734. doi: 10.5665/sleep.1846.
 6. Irwin M.R. Why sleep is important for health: A psychoneuroimmunology perspective. *Annu. Rev. Psychol.* 2015;66:143–172. doi: 10.1146/annurev-psych-010213-115205.
 7. Chokroverty S. Overview of sleep & sleep disorders. *Indian J. Med. Res.* 2010;131:126–140.[
 8. Institute of Medicine, Committee on Sleep Medicine and Research. The National Academies Collection: Reports funded by National Institutes of Health. In: Colten H.R., Altevogt B.M., editors. *Sleep Disorders and Sleep Deprivation: An Unmet Public Health Problem*. National Academy of Sciences; Washington, DC, USA: 2006.
 9. Liew S.C., Aung T. Sleep deprivation and its association with diseases—A review. *Sleep Med*. 2021;77:192–204. doi: 10.1016/j.sleep.2020.07.048.
 10. Andersen M.L., Tufik S. Vitamin D as an underlying factor in sleep-related issues. *J. Clin. Sleep Med. JCSM Off. Publ. Am. Acad. Sleep Med*. 2012;8:699. doi: 10.5664/jcsm.2268.
 11. Anglin R.E., Samaan Z., Walter S.D., McDonald S.D. Vitamin D deficiency and depression in adults: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Br. J. Psychiatry J. Ment. Sci.* 2013;202:100–107. doi: 10.1192/bjp.bp.111.106666.
 12. Romano F., Muscogiuri G., Di Benedetto E., Zhukouskaya V.V., Barrea L., Savastano S., Colao A., Di Somma C. Vitamin D and Sleep Regulation: Is there a Role for Vitamin D? *Curr. Pharm. Des.* 2020;26:2492–2496. doi: 10.2174/1381612826666200310145935.
 13. Muscogiuri G., Barrea L., Scannapieco M., Di Somma C., Scacchi M., Aimaretti G., Savastano S., Colao A., Marzullo P. The lullaby of the sun: The role of vitamin D in sleep disturbance. *Sleep Med*. 2019;54:262–265. doi: 10.1016/j.sleep.2018.10.033.
 14. Al-Shawwa B., Ehsan Z., Ingram D.G. Vitamin D and sleep in children. *J. Clin. Sleep Med. JCSM Off. Publ. Am. Acad. Sleep Med*. 2020;16:1119–1123. doi: 10.5664/jcsm.8440.
 15. Gao Q., Kou T., Zhuang B., Ren Y., Dong X., Wang Q. The Association between Vitamin D Deficiency and Sleep Disorders: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Nutrients*. 2018;10:1395. doi: 10.3390/nu10101395.
 16. Stumpf W.E., Bidmon H.J., Li L., Pilgrim C., Bartke A., Mayerhofer A., Heiss C. Nuclear receptor sites for vitamin D-soltriol in midbrain and hindbrain of Siberian hamster (*Phodopus sungorus*) assessed by autoradiography. *Histochemistry*. 1992;98:155–164. doi: 10.1007/BF00315874.
 17. Stumpf W.E., O'Brien L.P. 1,25 (OH)₂ vitamin D₃ sites of action in the brain. An autoradiographic study. *Histochemistry*. 1987;87:393–406. doi: 10.1007/BF00496810.
 18. Patrick R.P., Ames B.N. Vitamin D and the omega-3 fatty acids control serotonin synthesis and action, part 2: Relevance for ADHD, bipolar disorder, schizophrenia, and impulsive behavior. *FASEB J. Off. Publ. Fed. Am. Soc. Exp. Biol.* 2015;29:2207–2222. doi: 10.1096/fj.14-268342.
 19. Thorpy M. *Sleep Disorders Medicine*. Springer; Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany: 2017. International classification of sleep disorders; pp. 475–484.
 20. Higgins J.P.T., Savović J., Page M.J., Elbers R.G., Sterne J.A.C. Chapter 8: Assessing risk of bias in a randomized trial. In: Higgins J.P.T., Thomas J., Chandler J., Cumpston M., Li T., Page M.J., Welch V.A., editors. *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions Version 6.0*. Cochrane; Chichester, UK: 2019.
 21. Guyatt G.H., Oxman A.D., Vist G., Kunz R., Brozek J., Alonso-Coello P., Montori V., Akl E.A., Djulbegovic B., Falck-Ytter Y., et al. GRADE guidelines: 4. Rating the quality of evidence—study limitations (risk of bias) *J. Clin. Epidemiol.* 2011;64:407–415. doi: 10.1016/j.jclinepi.2010.07.017.
 22. Rethlefsen M.L., Kirtley S., Waffenschmidt S., Ayala A.P., Moher D., Page M.J., Koffel J.B. PRISMA-S: An extension to the PRISMA Statement for Reporting Literature Searches in Systematic Reviews. *Syst. Rev.* 2021;10:39. doi: 10.1186/s13643-020-01542-z.
 23. Page M.J., Moher D., Bossuyt P.M., Boutron I., Hoffmann T.C., Mulrow C.D., Shamseer L., Tetzlaff J.M., Akl E.A., Brennan S.E., et al. PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration: Updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*. 2021;372:n160. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n160.
 24. De Koning E.J., Lips P., Penninx B., Elders P.J.M., Heijboer A.C., den Heijer M., Bet P.M., van Marwijk H.W.J., van Schoor N.M. Vitamin D supplementation for the prevention of depression and poor physical function in older persons: The D-Vitaal study, a randomized clinical trial. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 2019;110:1119–1130. doi: 10.1093/ajcn/nqz141.
 25. Ghaderi A., Banafshe H.R., Motmaen M., Rasouli-Azad M., Bahmani F., Asemi Z. Clinical trial of the effects of vitamin D supplementation on psychological symptoms and metabolic profiles in maintenance methadone treatment patients. *Pt BProg. Neuro-Psychopharmacol. Biol. Psychiatry*. 2017;79:84–89. doi: 10.1016/j.pnpbp.2017.06.016.
 26. Kerley C.P., Hutchinson K., Bramham J., McGowan A., Faul J., Cormican L. Vitamin D Improves Selected Metabolic Parameters but Not Neuropsychological or Quality of Life Indices in OSA: A Pilot Study. *J. Clin. Sleep Med. JCSM Off. Publ. Am. Acad. Sleep Med*. 2017;13:19–26. doi: 10.5664/jcsm.6378.

27. Majid M.S., Ahmad H.S., Bizhan H., Hosein H.Z.M., Mohammad A. The effect of vitamin D supplement on the score and quality of sleep in 20–50 year-old people with sleep disorders compared with control group. *Nutr. Neurosci.* 2018;21:511–519. doi: 10.1080/1028415X.2017.1317395.
28. Mason C., de Dieu Tapsoba J., Duggan C., Wang C.Y., Korde L., McTiernan A. Repletion of vitamin D associated with deterioration of sleep quality among postmenopausal women. *Prev. Med.* 2016;93:166–170. doi: 10.1016/j.ypmed.2016.09.035.
29. McCarthy M.S., Elshaw E.B., Szekely B.M., Raju D. A Prospective Cohort Study of Vitamin D Supplementation in AD Soldiers: Preliminary Findings. *Mil. Med.* 2019;184((Suppl. S1)):498–505. doi: 10.1093/milmed/usy393.
30. Mirzaei A., Zabihyeganeh M., Jahed S.A., Khiabani E., Nojomi M., Ghaffari S. Effects of vitamin D optimization on quality of life of patients with fibromyalgia: A randomized controlled trial. *Med. J. Islamic Repub. Iran.* 2018;32:29. doi: 10.14196/mjiri.32.29.
31. Mohammadpour N., Jazayeri S., Tehrani-Doost M., Djalali M., Hosseini M., Effatpanah M., Davari-Ashtiani R., Karami E. Effect of vitamin D supplementation as adjunctive therapy to methylphenidate on ADHD symptoms: A randomized, double blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Nutr. Neurosci.* 2018;21:202–209. doi: 10.1080/1028415X.2016.1262097.
32. Okereke O.I., Reynolds C.F., 3rd, Mischoulon D., Chang G., Vyas C.M., Cook N.R., Weinberg A., Bubes V., Copeland T., Friedenberg G., et al. Effect of Long-term Vitamin D3 Supplementation vs Placebo on Risk of Depression or Clinically Relevant Depressive Symptoms and on Change in Mood Scores: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA.* 2020;324:471–480. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.10224.
33. Rorie A., Goldner W.S., Lyden E., Poole J.A. Beneficial role for supplemental vitamin D3 treatment in chronic urticaria: A randomized study. *Ann. Allergy Asthma Immunol. Off. Publ. Am. Coll. Allergy Asthma Immunol.* 2014;112:376–382. doi: 10.1016/j.anai.2014.01.010.
34. Sharifan P., Khoshakhlagh M., Khorasanchi Z., Darroudi S., Rezaie M., Safarian M., Vatanparast H., Afshari A., Ferns G., Ghazizadeh H., et al. Efficacy of low-fat milk and yogurt fortified with encapsulated vitamin D3 on improvement in symptoms of insomnia and quality of life: Evidence from the SUVINA trial. *Food Sci. Nutr.* 2020;8:4484–4490. doi: 10.1002/fsn3.1750.
35. Wali S.O., Abaalkhail B., Alhejaili F., Pandi-Perumal S.R. Efficacy of vitamin D replacement therapy in restless legs syndrome: A randomized control trial. *Sleep Breath. Schlaf Atm.* 2019;23:595–601. doi: 10.1007/s11325-018-1751-2.
36. Zhu C., Zhang Y., Wang T., Lin Y., Yu J., Xia Q., Zhu P., Zhu D.M. Vitamin D supplementation improves anxiety but not depression symptoms in patients with vitamin D deficiency. *Brain Behav.* 2020;10:e01760. doi: 10.1002/brb3.1760.
37. Slow S., Florkowski C.M., Chambers S.T., Priest P.C., Stewart A.W., Jennings L.C., Livesey J.H., Camargo C.A., Jr., Scragg R., Murdoch D.R. Effect of monthly vitamin D3 supplementation in healthy adults on adverse effects of earthquakes: Randomised controlled trial. *BMJ.* 2014;349:g7260. doi: 10.1136/bmj.g7260.
38. Aricò I., Campolo L., Silvestri R. Preliminary Data on Vitamin D Deficiency and Treatment in a Cohort of Sicilian RLS/WED Patients. *Neuropsychiatr. Dis. Treat.* 2014;10:953–958.
39. Eshaghi S., Morteza T., Khadijeh I., Knechtle B., Nikolaidis P.T., Chtourou H. The effect of aerobic training and vitamin D supplements on the neurocognitive functions of elderly women with sleep disorders. *Biol. Rhythm. Res.* 2020;51:727–734. doi: 10.1080/09291016.2019.1579884.]
40. Guler S., Yeşil G., Önal H., Ekici B., Ozdil M. Sleep disturbances and serum vitamin D levels in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Int. J. Clin. Exp. Med.* 2016;9:14691–14697.
41. Maheshwari P., Arun S., Venkatesh N., Sushmi K., Shanmugarajan T., Shanmugasundaram P. Effect of Vitamin D supplement in improving pain, sleep, and quality of life on patients with chronic low back pain. *Drug Invent. Today.* 2019;12:2508–2510.
42. Huang W., Shah S., Long Q., Crankshaw A.K., Tangpricha V. Improvement of pain, sleep, and quality of life in chronic pain patients with vitamin D supplementation. *Clin. J. Pain.* 2013;29:341–347. doi: 10.1097/AJP.0b013e318255655d.
43. Yan S., Tian Z., Zhao H., Wang C., Pan Y., Yao N., Guo Y., Wang H., Li B., Cui W. A meta-analysis: Does vitamin D play a promising role in sleep disorders? *Food Sci. Nutr.* 2020;8:5696–5709. doi: 10.1002/fsn3.1867.
44. Eyles D.W., Smith S., Kinobe R., Hewison M., McGrath J.J. Distribution of the vitamin D receptor and 1 alpha-hydroxylase in human brain. *J. Chem. Neuroanat.* 2005;29:21–30. doi: 10.1016/j.jchemneu.2004.08.006.
45. Garcion E., Wion-Barbot N., Montero-Menei C.N., Berger F., Wion D. New clues about vitamin D functions in the nervous system. *Trends Endocrinol. Metab. TEM.* 2002;13:100–105. doi: 10.1016/S1043-2760(01)00547-1.
46. Lucock M., Jones P., Martin C., Beckett E., Yates Z., Furst J., Veysey M. Vitamin D: Beyond Metabolism. *J. Evid. Based Complement. Altern. Med.* 2015;20:310–322. doi: 10.1177/2156587215580491.
47. Vitaterna M.H., Takahashi J.S., Turek F.W. Overview of circadian rhythms. *Alcohol Res. Health J. Natl. Inst. Alcohol Abus. Alcohol.* 2001;25:85–93.
48. Dibner C., Schibler U., Albrecht U. The mammalian circadian timing system: Organization and coordination of central and peripheral clocks. *Annu. Rev. Physiol.* 2010;72:517–549. doi: 10.1146/annurev-physiol-021909-135821.
49. Jamilian H., Amirani E., Milajerdi A., Kolahdooz F., Mirzaei H., Zaroudi M., Ghaderi A., Asemi Z. The effects of vitamin D supplementation on mental health, and biomarkers of inflammation and oxidative stress in patients with psychiatric disorders: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Prog. Neuro-Psychopharmacol. Biol. Psychiatry.* 2019;94:109651. doi: 10.1016/j.pnpbp.2019.109651.

50. Zhao D., Yu Y., Shen Y., Liu Q., Zhao Z., Sharma R., Reiter R.J. Melatonin Synthesis and Function: Evolutionary History in Animals and Plants. *Front. Endocrinol.* 2019;10:249. doi: 10.3389/fendo.2019.00249.
51. Kaneko I., Sabir M.S., Dussik C.M., Whitfield G.K., Karrys A., Hsieh J.C., Haussler M.R., Meyer M.B., Pike J.W., Jurutka P.W. 1,25-Dihydroxyvitamin D regulates expression of the tryptophan hydroxylase 2 and leptin genes: Implication for behavioral influences of vitamin D. *FASEB J. Off. Publ. Fed. Am. Soc. Exp. Biol.* 2015;29:4023–4035. doi: 10.1096/fj.14-269811.
52. Jablonski K.L., Chonchol M., Pierce G.L., Walker A.E., Seals D.R. 25-Hydroxyvitamin D deficiency is associated with inflammation-linked vascular endothelial dysfunction in middle-aged and older adults. *Hypertension.* 2011;57:63–69. doi: 10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.110.160929.
53. Krueger J.M., Majde J.A., Rector D.M. Cytokines in immune function and sleep regulation. *Handb. Clin. Neurol.* 2011;98:229–240. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-444-52006-7.00015-0.
54. Archontogeorgis K., Nena E., Papanas N., Steiropoulos P. The role of vitamin D in obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome. *Breathe.* 2018;14:206–215. doi: 10.1183/20734735.000618.
55. Chao Y.S., Brunel L., Faris P., Veugelers P.J. The importance of dose, frequency and duration of vitamin D supplementation for plasma 25-hydroxyvitamin D. *Nutrients.* 2013;5:4067–4078. doi: 10.3390/nu5104067.
56. Chakhtoura M., Chamoun N., Rahme M., Fuleihan G.E. Impact of vitamin D supplementation on falls and fractures-A critical appraisal of the quality of the evidence and an overview of the available guidelines. *Bone.* 2020;131:115112. doi: 10.1016/j.bone.2019.115112.
57. Caprio M., Infante M., Calanchini M., Mammi C., Fabbri A. Vitamin D: Not just the bone. Evidence for beneficial pleiotropic extraskelatal effects. *Eat. Weight Disord. EWD.* 2017;22:27–41. doi: 10.1007/s40519-016-0312-6.
58. Egierska D., Pietruszka P., Burzyńska P., Chruścicka I., Buchta J. Pleiotropic effects of vitamin D3. *J. Educ. Health Sport.* 2021;11:143–155. doi: 10.12775/JEHS.2021.11.07.013.